

Supplementary Files to the manuscript:

Discrete event simulation in R using the ‘simmer’ package for health economic modeling: a tutorial and illustration in colon cancer

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Appendix A: using the `simmer` package for health economic modelling

The `simmer` package has been developed by Iñaki Ucar and Bart Smeets to enable discrete event simulation (DES) in R. Although this tutorial mainly utilizes basic functions from the package, additional functions and related packages are available and more information on those can be found on the package's website: <https://r-simmer.org/>.

The `simmer` package uses two main objects to define and run a DES in R: the *trajectory* and the *simulation environment*. The *trajectory* represents the model structure that defines what happens to the simulated individuals, whereas the *simulation environment* determines how many individuals move through the trajectory, at what time point they enter the trajectory, and what information should be gathered about the individuals throughout the simulation. The *simulation environment* also contains the state of the simulation, including the information on the individuals that are in it. Section A.1 discusses *trajectories* in detail, Section A.2 focuses on *simulation environments*, and Section A.3 introduces *resources and capacity constraints*.

Note that this tutorial provides information about the main functions required to implement health economic simulation models and which are used in the case study. Informed by extensive experience with using the `simmer` package for health economic modelling, the provided information may go beyond what is covered in the standard package documentation for some functions, whereas the function documentation may provide further information on aspects that are not considered of primary interest for this health economic modeling tutorial.

Also note that in introducing the functions of the package, it is inevitable that some functions used to illustrate the use of another function, may not have been previously introduced at that point. Where this applies, the reader will be made aware, and code of primary interest will be highlighted in the corresponding text.

Throughout the remainder of this tutorial, coding examples will be provided in Code Boxes. In order to run the provided code, the `simmer` package and the `simmer.plot` package should be installed and loaded (see Code Box 1). This tutorial was written using R version 4.0.3, version 4.4.2 of the `simmer` package, and version 0.1.16 of the `simmer.plot` package.

Code Box 1. Installing and loading the packages so that the demonstration code can be run.

```
# If you have not already done so, install the packages  
install.packages(pkgs = c("simmer", "simmer.plot"));  
  
# Load the packages so their functions can be used  
library(simmer);  
library(simmer.plot);
```

A.1 Defining the model trajectory

Trajectories represent the structure of the model, defining what events the simulated individuals may experience and what actions are performed. Trajectories are defined using the `trajectory()` function. Although this function includes a `name` and `verbose` argument, these are optional. Calling the `trajectory()` function defines an empty trajectory, which can be expanded using different building blocks. The four main building blocks that are introduced here are *attributes*, *timeouts*, *branches* and *rollbacks*. Building blocks are most conveniently added to the trajectory using the chaining/piping workflow through the `%>%` function. Another helpful function is `join()`, which can be used to join trajectories together. The functions to add these building blocks are discussed in detail subsequently.

Trajectories can be visualized using the `plot()` function after loading the `simmer.plot` package. Plotting trajectories is very helpful for debugging and validating during model implementation.

Another helpful function during model development is the `log_()` function, which prints a message to the console. The `log_()` function requires the following arguments:

- `.traj` Trajectory object to which the `log_()` is to be added. This argument is not typically used as this information is provided by chaining/piping (`%>%`).
- `message` A string or object that returns a string specifying the message that is to be printed to the console.

A basic illustration of how a trajectory is defined and plotted is provided in Code Box 2. The trajectory includes a `log_()` function to display a message. The code also illustrates how a simulation is defined and run, which will be discussed in detail later. For now, it is sufficient to know that 5 individuals are simulated and that they all enter the trajectory at time $t = 0$. The following subsections discuss functions that can be used to define more advanced trajectories.

Code Box 2. Defining and plotting a basic trajectory and defining and running a simulation.

```
# Defining and plotting a basic trajectory
trajectory_basic <- trajectory() %>%
  log_(message = "Hello World!");

plot(trajectory_basic);

# Defining the simulation
sim <- simmer() %>%
  add_generator(name_prefix = "Patient_",
               trajectory = trajectory_basic,
               distribution = at(rep(x = 0, times = 5)));

sim %>% run();

## 0: Patient_0: Hello World!
## 0: Patient_1: Hello World!
## 0: Patient_2: Hello World!
## 0: Patient_3: Hello World!
## 0: Patient_4: Hello World!

## simmer environment: anonymous | now: 0 | next:
## { Monitor: in memory }
## { Source: Patient_ | monitored: 1 | n_generated: 5 }
```

A.1.1 Attributes

Attributes represent information about variables on an individual or global level. Individual-level attributes are tracked for each individual separately (e.g., the individual's age, sex, or disease severity), whereas global variables are shared amongst individuals (e.g., a discount rate). These attributes are identified by *keys* (i.e., names) and can only have numerical values. The values of attributes can be updated throughout the simulation.

Attributes play an important role in DES, as they can store information that influence which events occur and the time at which those events occur. In line with their importance, learning how to use attributes may be considered the most strenuous part of this tutorial. There are two actions when it comes to using attributes: *setting* their values and *getting* their values.

Setting values for individual-level and global attributes is done through the `set_attribute()` and `set_global()` functions, respectively, which both have the following arguments:

- `.traj` Trajectory object to which the `set_attribute()` / `set_global()` call is to be added. This argument is not typically used as this information is provided by chaining/piping (`%>%`).
- `keys` String vector that defines the names of the attributes that are to be set or updated. This allows setting or updating the value of multiple attributes at once.
- `values` Numerical vector that defines the values to be used to set or update the attributes. When multiple attributes are set or updated, the order of the values should match the order of the *keys*.
- `mod` Character suggesting a mathematical expression that is used to modify the pre-updated values of the attributes using the values provided. The options are: NA, “+” and “*”. If `mod = NA`, which is the default, the attribute(s) will be *set* to the provided

value(s). If `mod = "+"`, the specified value will be *added* to the current value of the attribute, whereas the current value will be multiplied by the specified value if `mod = "*"` . For example, if the value of an attribute was previously set to 10 and the current call of the `set_attribute()` function includes `values = 5` and `mod = "+"`, the updated value of the attribute will be $10 + 5 = 15$. Incrementally adding costs to an attribute that tracks the total costs is an example where the *mod* argument is useful.

- `init` Numerical vector that defines the initial values for the attributes if the *mod* argument is used, but the attributes have not been defined previously. In that scenario, it is not known what value should be modified, so that information is provided by the *init* argument. If no value for *init* is provide, the default is assumed to be zero.

Important in setting the *values* using a function is that the code needs to identify whether this function is to be evaluated once when the trajectory is defined, or every time when a simulated individual reaches that part of the trajectory. If the *value* argument of the `set_attribute()` function is specified as a `function()`, it is dynamic in a way that the subsequent function is evaluated every time an individual reaches it. Otherwise, the function is only evaluated once when defining the trajectory and, consequently, every time the `set_attribute()` call is performed, that same value will be used. This is illustrated in Code Box 3 for a hypothetical attribute *age* that is to be defined according to a Normal distribution with a mean of 60 and standard deviation of 5. When the simulation is run using `trajectory_static`, the random draw from the normal distribution is performed once, whereas the random draw is performed for every individual separately when it is defined as a `function()`. This code includes the use of the `get_attribute()` function within the `log_()` function, which will be introduced subsequently. For now, it is sufficient to focus on the difference in the specification of the *values* argument for the `set_attribute()` function and the impact that has on the attribute values that are printed using the `log_()` function.

Code Box 3. Illustration of the importance of specifying that values are dynamic (i.e., are to be evaluated every time an individual passes) when a function is used to set an attribute value.

```
# Static trajectory in which one sample for age is drawn when defining the
# trajectory object, which is then used for all simulated individuals
trajectory_static <- trajectory() %>%
  set_attribute(keys = "age",
               values = rnorm(n = 1, mean = 60, sd = 5)) %>%
  log_(message = function() as.character(get_attribute(.env = sim,
                                                       keys = "age"))));

# Dynamic trajectory in which the value is defined as a function sampling from
# the Normal distribution every time it is called
trajectory_dynamic <- trajectory() %>%
  set_attribute(keys = "age",
               values = function() rnorm(n = 1, mean = 60, sd = 5)) %>%
  log_(message = function() as.character(get_attribute(.env = sim,
                                                       keys = "age"))));

# Running the simulation for 5 individuals using the static trajectory
sim <- simmer() %>%
  add_generator(name_prefix = "Patient_",
               trajectory = trajectory_static,
               distribution = at(rep(x = 0, times = 5)));

sim %>% run();

## 0: Patient_0: 58.7151015513567
## 0: Patient_1: 58.7151015513567
## 0: Patient_2: 58.7151015513567
## 0: Patient_3: 58.7151015513567
## 0: Patient_4: 58.7151015513567

## simmer environment: anonymous | now: 0 | next:
## { Monitor: in memory }
## { Source: Patient_ | monitored: 1 | n_generated: 5 }

# Running the simulation for 5 individuals using the dynamic trajectory
sim <- simmer() %>%
  add_generator(name_prefix = "Patient_",
               trajectory = trajectory_dynamic,
               distribution = at(rep(x = 0, times = 5)));

sim %>% run();

## 0: Patient_0: 63.4650064926893
## 0: Patient_1: 68.7274345766544
## 0: Patient_2: 62.3719997812715
## 0: Patient_3: 53.5417146332858
## 0: Patient_4: 56.7546604199856

## simmer environment: anonymous | now: 0 | next:
## { Monitor: in memory }
## { Source: Patient_ | monitored: 1 | n_generated: 5 }
```

Getting the values of individual-level or global attributes at a certain point in the simulation is done using the `get_attribute()` and `get_global()` functions, respectively, which both have the following arguments:

- `.env` Simulation environment in which the attributes are monitored.
- `keys` String vector that defines the names of the attributes that you want to get the values of. If multiple attributes are requested at once, an unnamed vector is returned including the values of the attributes in the corresponding order.

An illustration of the `get_attribute()` function has been provided in Code Box 3. Importantly, as demonstrated in the code, the `get_attribute()` function also needs to be used in conjunction with a `function()` statement. If such a statement is not used, the function will be evaluated at the time of defining the trajectory, which will either generate an error or result in a static value being obtained from the specified *simulation environment*, both generally being undesirable.

A.1.2 Timeouts

Timeouts, which can also be referred to delays, are used to control the duration of time between different events. An individual can be delayed for a certain amount of time using the `timeout()` function, which has the following arguments:

- `.traj` Trajectory object to which the `timeout()` call is to be added. This argument is not typically used as this information is provided by chaining/piping (`%>%`).
- `task` Numerical that defines the duration of the timeout, i.e., delay.

As for the previously introduced functions, a `function()` statement needs to be included when using a function to define `task`. Note that no unit for the time is defined within this function,

so the modeler needs to ensure the time unit is consistent throughout the model. Code box 4 extends the code in Code Box 2 to illustrate how five individuals are delayed using random draws from a Weibull distribution. The simulation output shows that the simulated individuals all trigger the message to be send at a different point in time.

Code Box 4. Delaying individuals using a timeout.

```
# Defining the trajectory with a timeout
trajectory_timeout <- trajectory() %>%
  timeout(task = function() rweibull(n = 1, shape = .5, scale = 8)) %>%
  log_(message = "Hello World!");

# Defining the simulation
sim <- simmer() %>%
  add_generator(name_prefix = "Patient_",
               trajectory = trajectory_timeout,
               distribution = at(rep(x = 0, times = 5)));

# Running the simulation
sim %>% run();

## 0.000740717: Patient_0: Hello World!
## 0.00555399: Patient_4: Hello World!
## 0.634176: Patient_3: Hello World!
## 78.3912: Patient_1: Hello World!
## 214.57: Patient_2: Hello World!

## simmer environment: anonymous | now: 214.569905985589 | next:
## { Monitor: in memory }
## { Source: Patient_ | monitored: 1 | n_generated: 5 }
```

In health economic models, it is typically useful to save the time to a specific event in an individual-level attribute, for example to calculate quality-adjusted life years (QALYs) or for validation purposes. Therefore, the `timeout_from_attribute()` function that reads the time directly from an attribute will be often used to implement timeouts. Similarly, the `timeout_from_global()` function can be used for timeouts based on a global variable. These functions have the following arguments:

- `.traj` Trajectory object to which the `timeout_from_attribute()` / `timeout_from_global()` call is to be added. This argument is not typically used as this information is provided by chaining/piping (`%>%`).
- `keys` Character defining the name of the attribute that contains the value for the timeout, i.e., the value that would be provided as `task` to the `timeout()` function.

Code Box 5 illustrates how a timeout based on an attribute can be implemented by first storing the value for the timeout in an attribute called `t_delay` and subsequently applying the timeout. Two ways for applying the timeout are illustrated: using the standard `timeout()` function and reading the attribute value using the `get_attribute()` function or using the `timeout_from_attribute()` function. The first option is illustrated to provide an understanding of what happens in the `timeout_from_attribute()` function. Note that the random number seed is set using the `set.seed()` function before running the simulations, so that the same values are drawn from the Weibull distribution in both runs.

Code Box 5. Delaying individuals based on values stored attributes.

```
# Defining the trajectory with a timeout using the timeout() function after
# first setting the value to an attribute
trajectory_timeout_standard <- trajectory() %>%
  set_attribute(keys = "t_delay",
               values = function() rweibull(n = 1, shape = .5, scale = 8)) %>%
  timeout(task = function() get_attribute(.env = sim, keys = "t_delay")) %>%
  log_(message = "Hello World!");

# Defining the trajectory with a timeout using the timeout_from_attribute()
# function after first setting the value to an attribute
trajectory_timeout_attribute <- trajectory() %>%
  set_attribute(keys = "t_delay",
               values = function() rweibull(n = 1, shape = .5, scale = 8)) %>%
  timeout_from_attribute(key = "t_delay") %>%
  log_(message = "Hello World!");

# Defining and running the simulation for trajectory_timeout_standard
sim <- simmer() %>%
  add_generator(name_prefix = "Patient_",
               trajectory = trajectory_timeout_standard,
               distribution = at(rep(x = 0, times = 5)));

set.seed(1); sim %>% run();

## 0.0741619: Patient_3: Hello World!
## 2.48311: Patient_2: Hello World!
## 7.81751: Patient_1: Hello World!
## 14.0685: Patient_0: Hello World!
## 20.5072: Patient_4: Hello World!

## simmer environment: anonymous | now: 20.507232634479 | next:
## { Monitor: in memory }
## { Source: Patient_ | monitored: 1 | n_generated: 5 }

# Defining and running the simulation for trajectory_timeout_attribute
sim <- simmer() %>%
  add_generator(name_prefix = "Patient_",
               trajectory = trajectory_timeout_attribute,
               distribution = at(rep(x = 0, times = 5)));

set.seed(1); sim %>% run();

## 0.0741619: Patient_3: Hello World!
## 2.48311: Patient_2: Hello World!
## 7.81751: Patient_1: Hello World!
## 14.0685: Patient_0: Hello World!
## 20.5072: Patient_4: Hello World!

## simmer environment: anonymous | now: 20.507232634479 | next:
## { Monitor: in memory }
## { Source: Patient_ | monitored: 1 | n_generated: 5 }
```

A.1.3 Branches

Branches are used to allocate individuals to different sub-trajectories, i.e., fork the trajectory, based on a certain condition. A common example where branches are implemented is in case of competing events, such as recurrence and death in oncology case studies. Individuals who experienced a cancer recurrence may enter a trajectory that includes treatment for advanced disease, whereas those without recurrence may not. Branches are implemented using the `branch()` function, which has the following arguments:

- `.traj` Trajectory object to which the `branch()` call is to be added. This argument is not typically used as this information is provided by chaining/piping (`%>%`).
- `option` Function that returns an integer number that indicates to which sub-trajectory in the branch the individual is to be allocated, based on the order in which the sub-trajectories are listed in the script. A value of 1 will direct the individual to the first trajectory, a value of 2 will direct the individual to the second trajectory, and so on. Importantly, a value of 0 will result in the individual skipping the branch. Note that a `function()` statement is required for this argument.
- `continue` Boolean (i.e., logical) vector that defines for each sub-trajectory whether the individual should continue beyond the branch after they completed the sub-trajectory they were directed to. A `TRUE` value indicates that the individual should continue beyond the branch and a `FALSE` value indicates that the individual should not continue after completing the sub-trajectory in the branch, i.e., the simulation ends for that specific individual.
- `...` Trajectory objects that represent the options, i.e., sub-trajectories, in the branch. The sub-trajectories are separated by commas. The number of sub-trajectories should be equal to the length of the logical vector provided to the `continue` argument

and to the number of non-zero values that can theoretically be returned by the function used for the `option` argument. The trajectories can either be defined using the `trajectory()` function within the branch or by referring to a separately defined trajectory (both will be illustrated).

Code Box 6 demonstrates the implementation of a basic branch with two options, i.e., sub-trajectories. Individuals are randomly allocated to a sub-trajectory or to skip the branch using the `sample()` function that returns a 0, 1, or 2. When they enter a sub-trajectory a message is printed, and similar if they leave or skip the branch. Note that those directed to the first sub-trajectory will continue beyond the branch, whereas those directed to the second sub-trajectory will not. The output shows that Patients 0, 2, and 4 skipped the branch, Patient 3 entered the first sub-trajectory and continued, and Patient 1 entered the second sub-trajectory and remained there. By plotting the `trajectory_branch` object using the `plot()` function (after loading the `simmer.plot` package), the branch can be visualized. Code Box 7 illustrates how a branch can be implemented using pre-specified sub-trajectories and based on a saved attribute. Using pre-specified sub-trajectories is particularly helpful for debugging or when a specific sub-trajectory is used in multiple branches.

Code Box 6. Branching trajectories.

```
# Defining the trajectory with a branch
trajectory_branch <- trajectory() %>%
  branch(option = function() sample(x = 0:2, size = 1),
         continue = c(TRUE, FALSE),

         # option = 1
         trajectory() %>%
           log_(message = "Entered the first branch!"),

         # option = 2
         trajectory() %>%
           log_(message = "Entered the second branch!"))

) %>%
log_(message = "Skipped or left the branch!");

# Defining the simulation
sim <- simmer() %>%
  add_generator(name_prefix = "Patient_",
               trajectory = trajectory_branch,
               distribution = at(rep(x = 0, times = 5)));

# Running the simulation
set.seed(1); sim %>% run();

## 0: Patient_0: Skipped or left the branch!
## 0: Patient_1: Entered the second branch!
## 0: Patient_2: Skipped or left the branch!
## 0: Patient_3: Entered the first branch!
## 0: Patient_3: Skipped or left the branch!
## 0: Patient_4: Skipped or left the branch!

## simmer environment: anonymous | now: 0 | next:
## { Monitor: in memory }
## { Source: Patient_ | monitored: 1 | n_generated: 5 }
```

Code Box 7. Branching trajectories based on attributes and using pre-specified sub-trajectories.

```
# Defining the sub-trajectories for use in the branch
sub_trajectory_1 <- trajectory() %>%
  log_(message = "Entered the first branch!");

sub_trajectory_2 <- trajectory() %>%
  log_(message = "Entered the second branch!");

# Defining the main trajectory with a branch based on a saved attribute
trajectory_branch_advanced <- trajectory() %>%
  set_attribute(keys = "i_branch",
               values = function() sample(x = 0:2, size = 1)) %>%
  branch(option = function() get_attribute(.env = sim, keys = "i_branch"),
         continue = c(TRUE, FALSE),

         # option = 1
         sub_trajectory_1,

         # option = 2
         sub_trajectory_2

  ) %>%
  log_(message = "Skipped or left the branch!");

# Defining the simulation
sim <- simmer() %>%
  add_generator(name_prefix = "Patient_",
               trajectory = trajectory_branch_advanced,
               distribution = at(rep(x = 0, times = 5)));

# Running the simulation
set.seed(1); sim %>% run();

## 0: Patient_0: Skipped or left the branch!
## 0: Patient_1: Entered the second branch!
## 0: Patient_2: Skipped or left the branch!
## 0: Patient_3: Entered the first branch!
## 0: Patient_3: Skipped or left the branch!
## 0: Patient_4: Skipped or left the branch!

## simmer environment: anonymous | now: 0 | next:
## { Monitor: in memory }
## { Source: Patient_ | monitored: 1 | n_generated: 5 }
```

A.1.4 Rollbacks

Rollbacks can be used to repeat sections of the trajectory by moving an individual a certain number of steps back in the trajectory. This is helpful, for example, when modelling repetitive activities, such as treatment cycles. Rollback are implemented using the `rollback()` function, which has the following arguments:

- `.traj` Trajectory object to which the `rollback()` call is to be added. This argument is not typically used as this information is provided by chaining/piping (`%>%`).
- `amount` Integer indicating the number of activities (i.e., functions in the trajectory) to rollback.
- `times` Integer indicating how often the individual can rollback. `Inf` can be used when the number of rollbacks is controlled by the `check` argument or differently in the trajectory.
- `check` Function that returns a logical value (i.e., boolean) indicating whether a rollback is to be performed. If the `check` argument is used, the `times` is ignored.

Code Box 8 illustrates two ways to implement a rollback so that an individual twice triggers a message to be printed. The first approach uses the `times` argument, whereas the second uses the `check` argument in combination with an attribute that counts the number of messages that have been printed. The `check` argument will typically be used for scenarios in which the condition for a rollback depends on more than a simple count. The number of rollbacks can also be controlled by implementing the rollback in a branch. Note that the number of simulated individuals is set to two to control the length of the simulation output. When implementing rollbacks, plotting the trajectory is helpful in making sure the `amount` argument is specified correctly.

Code Box 8. Using rollbacks to repeat sections of code.

```
# Defining the trajectory with a rollback and directly specifying the number
# of times the rollback is to be applied
trajectory_rollback_times <- trajectory() %>%
  log_(message = "Hello World!") %>%
  rollback(amount = 1, times = 1);

# Defining the trajectory with a rollback and checking whether another rollback
# is to be performed based on an attribute
trajectory_rollback_check <- trajectory() %>%
  log_(message = "Hello World!") %>%
  set_attribute(keys = "n_messages", values = 1, mod = "+") %>%
  rollback(amount = 2,
           check = function() 2 > get_attribute(.env = sim,
                                               keys = "n_messages"));

# Defining and running the simulation for trajectory trajectory_rollback_times
sim <- simmer() %>%
  add_generator(name_prefix = "Patient_",
               trajectory = trajectory_rollback_times,
               distribution = at(rep(x = 0, times = 2)));

sim %>% run();

## 0: Patient_0: Hello World!
## 0: Patient_0: Hello World!
## 0: Patient_1: Hello World!
## 0: Patient_1: Hello World!

## simmer environment: anonymous | now: 0 | next:
## { Monitor: in memory }
## { Source: Patient_ | monitored: 1 | n_generated: 2 }

# Defining and running the simulation for trajectory trajectory_rollback_check
sim <- simmer() %>%
  add_generator(name_prefix = "Patient_",
               trajectory = trajectory_rollback_check,
               distribution = at(rep(x = 0, times = 2)));

sim %>% run();

## 0: Patient_0: Hello World!
## 0: Patient_0: Hello World!
## 0: Patient_1: Hello World!
## 0: Patient_1: Hello World!

## simmer environment: anonymous | now: 0 | next:
## { Monitor: in memory }
## { Source: Patient_ | monitored: 1 | n_generated: 2 }
```

A.1.5 Joining trajectories

Trajectories can be merged by joining them using the `join()` function. This may be helpful when a sub-trajectory is used multiple times to define the overall model structure. The `join()` function has no specific arguments other than the trajectories that are to be joined, separated by commas. Use of the `join()` function to add a pre-specified sub-trajectory to another trajectory is illustrated in Code Box 9.

Code Box 9. Joining trajectories.

```
# Defining a trajectory that is to be joined with the main trajectory
trajectory_to_be_merged <- trajectory() %>%
  log_(message = "Hello Again!")

# Defining the main trajectory with the sub_trajectory included
trajectory_main <- trajectory() %>%
  log_(message = "Hello World!") %>%
  join(trajectory_to_be_merged);

# Defining the simulation
sim <- simmer() %>%
  add_generator(name_prefix = "Patient_",
               trajectory = trajectory_main,
               distribution = at(rep(x = 0, times = 2)));

# Running the simulation
sim %>% run();

## 0: Patient_0: Hello World!
## 0: Patient_0: Hello Again!
## 0: Patient_1: Hello World!
## 0: Patient_1: Hello Again!

## simmer environment: anonymous | now: 0 | next:
## { Monitor: in memory }
## { Source: Patient_ | monitored: 1 | n_generated: 2 }
```

A.2 Defining and running the simulation

After defining the trajectory, the simulation can be performed by *generating* individuals that will run through the trajectory. As has been illustrated before, simulations are defined using the `simmer()` function that has an optional `name` and `verbose` argument. The function also has an optional `mon` and `log_level` argument, which are for more advanced use and typically not required. Calling the `simmer()` function defines an empty simulation environment, which can be expanded using different building blocks. The main building block for health economic simulations will be the *generator*. After defining the simulation environment, the simulation can be performed and, subsequently, the simulation outcomes can be extracted. The following sections discuss each of these steps in detail.

A.2.1 Defining the simulation environment

The `add_generator()` function is used to add a specific type of individuals to the simulation environment. It has several arguments that provide control of the simulation:

- `.env` Simulation environment to which the `add_generator()` call is to be added. This argument is not typically used as this information is provided by chaining/piping (`%>%`).
- `name_prefix` String indicating the name prefix for the simulated individuals.
- `trajectory` Trajectory object through which the individuals will flow.
- `distribution` Function returning the interarrival times, with a negative value stopping the generator.
- `mon` Integer defining the level of monitoring for the simulated individuals: 0 = no monitoring, 1 = simple monitoring, 2 = level 1 + attribute monitoring. In health

economic models, outcomes will be recorded using attributes and, hence, a monitoring level of 2 is generally preferable.

The additional `priority`, `preemptible`, and `restart` arguments are optional arguments that are relevant when modelling resources and capacity constraints and are, therefore, not discussed here. As has been demonstrated in the Code Boxes before, the `at()` function can be used to define the arrival times rather than the interarrival times for the `distribution` argument. This is particularly helpful for health economic analyses, as it is often preferable that all individuals start the simulation at $t = 0$ for convenient discounting routines based on the simulation time.

A.2.2 Running the simulation

After a simulation environment has been defined, the simulation can be performed using the `run()` function. The `.env` argument of this function can be used to specify the simulation environment to be simulated or, alternatively, a pipe (`%>%`) can be used to link the two. The `until` argument determines how many time units are to be simulated. If it is not specified, the default value `Inf` ensures the simulation ends once all events have occurred. The other `progress`, `steps`, and `n` arguments are optional. Because a simulation environment can be used to perform multiple simulation runs, it can be considered good practice to first define the environment and add the generator, and in a separate pipe run the simulation, as has been illustrated in the code throughout.

Another useful simulation-related function is the `now()` function, which can be used within a trajectory to obtain the current simulation time. Like for the `get_attribute()` function, the simulation environment for which the simulation time is to be obtained needs to be specified

through the `.env` argument. Code Box 10 illustrates how the `now()` function can be used in a `log_()` call to print the current simulation time between two timeouts.

Code Box 10 also illustrates how the `reset()` function should be used to reset a completed simulation before starting a new one. If a simulation environment is not reset, it will continue running from the time where it was stopped. This is also illustrated in this code by running the simulation for 10 time units by specifying the `until` argument in the `run()` function.

A.2.3 Extracting the simulation output

If attributes are monitored in the simulation by setting `mon = 2` when calling the `add_generator()` function, the `get_mon_attributes()` can be used to extract the monitored attribute values from the simulation environment. This is illustrated for two individuals in Code Box 11, which shows how the values of the only attribute *survival* have changed throughout the simulation. Note that the `mon = 2` statement was added to the `add_generator()` call.

Code Box 10. Running and resetting simulations and obtaining the current simulation time.

```
# Defining a trajectory to print the current simulation time between timeouts
trajectory_now <- trajectory() %>%
  timeout(task = function() rweibull(n = 1, shape = .5, scale = 8)) %>%
  log_(message = function() paste("The current time is:", now(.env = sim))) %>%
  timeout(task = function() rweibull(n = 1, shape = .5, scale = 8));

# Defining the simulation
sim <- simmer() %>%
  add_generator(name_prefix = "Patient_",
               trajectory = trajectory_now,
               distribution = at(rep(x = 0, times = 2)));

# Running the simulation for 10 time units
set.seed(1); sim %>% run(until = 10);

## 7.81751: Patient_1: The current time is: 7.81750744376276

## simmer environment: anonymous | now: 10 | next: 10.3006180738886
## { Monitor: in memory }
## { Source: Patient_ | monitored: 1 | n_generated: 2 }

# Completing the simulation
sim %>% run();

## 14.0685: Patient_0: The current time is: 14.0684953749934

## simmer environment: anonymous | now: 14.1426572909786 | next:
## { Monitor: in memory }
## { Source: Patient_ | monitored: 1 | n_generated: 2 }

# Running the simulation without resetting will not have any impact
set.seed(1); sim %>% run();

## simmer environment: anonymous | now: 14.1426572909786 | next:
## { Monitor: in memory }
## { Source: Patient_ | monitored: 1 | n_generated: 2 }

# After resetting, the simulation will start over
set.seed(1); sim %>% reset() %>% run();

## 7.81751: Patient_1: The current time is: 7.81750744376276
## 14.0685: Patient_0: The current time is: 14.0684953749934

## simmer environment: anonymous | now: 14.1426572909786 | next:
## { Monitor: in memory }
## { Source: Patient_ | monitored: 1 | n_generated: 2 }
```

Code Box 11. Extracting monitored attributes from a simulation environment.

```
# Defining and a basic trajectory that captures survival
trajectory_output <- trajectory() %>%
  set_attribute(keys = "survival", values = 0) %>%
  timeout(task = function() rweibull(n = 1, shape = .5, scale = 8)) %>%
  set_attribute(keys = "survival", values = function() now(.env = sim));

# Defining the simulation
sim <- simmer() %>%
  add_generator(name_prefix = "Patient_",
               trajectory = trajectory_output,
               distribution = at(rep(x = 0, times = 2)),
               mon = 2);

# Running the simulation
sim %>% run();

## simmer environment: anonymous | now: 20.507232634479 | next:
## { Monitor: in memory }
## { Source: Patient_ | monitored: 2 | n_generated: 2 }

# Extracting the simulation output
df_sim_out <- get_mon_attributes(sim);

head(df_sim_out);

##           time      name      key      value replication
## 1  0.00000000 Patient_0 survival  0.00000000           1
## 2  0.00000000 Patient_1 survival  0.00000000           1
## 3  0.09185131 Patient_1 survival  0.09185131           1
## 4 20.50723263 Patient_0 survival 20.50723263           1
```

A.3 Including resources and capacity constraints

Resources and resource capacity constraints are an integral part of DES. Although resource constraints are not considered in the case study, the `simmer` package allows resources to be included in a straightforward way. The flexibility of `simmer` is an important reason for selecting it as the platform for this tutorial. Implementing resources in a model involves defining their use in the *trajectory* using the `seize()` and `release()` functions and specifying how many resources are available in the *simulation environment* using the `add_resource()` function,

similar to the use of the `add_generator()` function for defining how many individuals should be simulated.

The `seize()` function seizes one or multiple units of the same resource in a trajectory, whereas the `release()` function releases the previously seized resources. If no resource is available when an individual tries to seize it, that individual will enter the queue until the required resource become available. The parameters for the queue, such as maximum queue size, can be defined in the simulation environment. Although especially the `seize()` function has several additional, more advanced arguments, both the `seize()` and `release()` functions have the following key arguments:

- `.traj` Trajectory object to which the `seize()/release()` is to be added. This argument is not typically used as this information is provided by chaining/piping (`%>%`).
- `resource` String specifying the name of the resource to be seized or released. This name has to match the name of the resource specified in the simulation environment.
- `amount` Number indicating the amount of the resource to be seized or released.

The `add_resource()` function specifies a resource to be available in the *simulation environment*. In addition to some more advanced arguments, the `add_resource()` function has the following key arguments:

- `.env` Simulation environment to which the `add_resource()` call is to be added. This argument is not typically used as this information is provided by chaining/piping (`%>%`).
- `name` String specifying the name of the resource. This name is defined here and referred to from the `seize()` and `release()` functions within a trajectory.

- `capacity` Numeric defining the amount of the resource to be available. In defining the `capacity`, the `schedule()` function can be used to define how the `capacity` changes over time, if applicable.
- `queue_size` Numeric defining the maximum number of individuals that can be in the queue for the resource. In defining the `queue_size`, the `schedule()` function can be used to define how the `queue_size` changes over time, if applicable.

The `schedule()` function can be used to define how the `capacity` and `queue_size` of a resource change over time, if that is applicable. The `schedule()` function has three arguments:

- `timetable` Numeric vector specifying the time point at which the value should change.
- `values` Numeric vector specifying the capacity for each point in time specified in the `timetable` argument.
- `period` Numeric defining the period over which the schedule is repeated.

Code Box 12 illustrates how these functions can be used to model a general practice setting. In the example, three patients arrive at the GP in the morning and are seen by the GP one-by-one. If the simulation time is in hours, the patients arrive 7:45am, whereas the GP arrives at 8am. The patients' arrival is defined in the `add_generator()` function, whereas a `schedule()` is used in the `add_resource()` function to specify that one unit of GP is available from 8am. Consequently, the simulation output shows that all the patients arrive at simulation time 7.75, but that the first patient is seen at time 8 when the GP arrives. Subsequently, the patients are seen one-by-one with different durations for the consultations sampled from a distribution. Similar to the `get_mon_attributes()` function, information about the resources can be extracted and plotted using the `get_mon_resources()` and `get_mon_arrivals()` attributes.

Code Box 12. Illustration of a general practice where one GP (resource) is available to see three patients that come in just before the practice opens.

```
# Defining and a basic trajectory with resources
trajectory_GP <- trajectory() %>%
  log_(message = "I have arrived in the waiting room.") %>%
  seize(resource = "GP") %>%
  log_(message = "I am now seen by the GP.") %>%
  timeout(task = function() rweibull(1, 2, 0.5)) %>%
  log_(message = "Feeling much better now and ready to go home!") %>%
  release(resource = "GP");

# Defining the simulation with patients who arrive at time 7.75 (i.e., 7:45am)
# and a single GP who arrives at time 8 (i.e., 8:00am)
sim <- simmer() %>%
  add_resource(name = "GP",
              capacity = schedule(timetable=c(0,8), values=c(0,1))) %>%
  add_generator(name_prefix = "Patient_",
              trajectory = trajectory_GP,
              distribution = at(rep(x = 7.75, times = 3)));

# Running the simulation
sim %>% run();

## 7.75: Patient_0: I have arrived in the waiting room.
## 7.75: Patient_1: I have arrived in the waiting room.
## 7.75: Patient_2: I have arrived in the waiting room.
## 8: Patient_0: I am now seen by the GP.
## 8.11928: Patient_0: Feeling much better now and ready to go home!
## 8.11928: Patient_1: I am now seen by the GP.
## 8.44112: Patient_1: Feeling much better now and ready to go home!
## 8.44112: Patient_2: I am now seen by the GP.
## 8.7815: Patient_2: Feeling much better now and ready to go home!

## simmer environment: anonymous | now: 8.78150003425918 | next:
## { Monitor: in memory }
## { Resource: GP | monitored: TRUE | server status: 0(1) | queue status: 0(Inf
```